

Damage in hybrid jointed Glare structures under the quasi-static loading

Peifei Xu, Zhengong Zhou*

Center for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, China

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the progression of damage in bolt jointed and hybrid (bolt/bonded) jointed GLARE structures through a series of tests, including double cantilever beam experiments, end notched flexure experiments and tensile tests. Numerical simulations of tensile tests on bolt and bonded jointed GLARE structures are performed using finite element software ABAQUS. The experimental and numerical results provide evidence that delamination is the dominant failure mode as a result of the weak interlaminar strength between the metal and the glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) layers and the secondary bending moment. Bearing damage occurs mainly around the bolt hole, and the matrix with 90° directional fibers is damaged more easily than the layer with 0° directional fibers. A suggestion is proposed to design the optimal hybrid jointed GLARE structures by adjusting the stiffness of the liquid shim.

Experimental Procedure

- Axial tensile tests
- DCB experiments
- ENF experiments

Results and discussions

- Out-of-plane displacement
- The results form the secondary bending moment

- Multiple Damage patterns
- Delamination between metal and fiber layers
- Plastic deformation of aluminum
- Compression failure of GFRP

weight ratio of adhesive and microsphere 5:1

- Displacement-load curves
- Mode I fracture toughness
- Displacement-load curves
- Mode II fracture toughness

Conclusions

The length of legend represents the destructiveness of each layer.

- The failure of aluminum alloy plane resulted from the deflection of fastener compression.
- The matrix of GFRP layers with 90° directional fibers was damaged most seriously because of no fiber reinforcement.
- Most delamination failure occurred around the bolt hole.
- The stiffness of liquid shim should agree with the stiffness of the jointed GLARE structure.